

Ranking factors affecting the decontamination efficacy of non-thermal plasma: The approach of dissipated power per plasma volume through machine learning modeling

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ABSTRACT

Non-thermal plasma treatment can preserve food, but a meta-analysis assessing its efficacy has not been performed. This study retrieved the inactivation kinetics parameter $\log_{10}D$ ($n = 519$), which varied largely among different plasma setups. Atmospheric pressure plasma jet, corona discharge, surface barrier discharge, dielectric barrier discharge, and inductively-coupled plasma had the highest efficacy with median D -values under 2 min. Dielectric barrier discharge, the most frequent setup ($n = 160$), was analyzed using dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3) as an integrated predictor of decontamination efficacy. Using conventional and machine learning approaches the most correlated parameters to the $\log_{10}D$ were: dissipated power per plasma volume and matrix category, followed by microbial genus and pH. This study uses active learning to improve literature screening for data collection and various data analysis techniques for data treatment and ranking of the factors affecting non-thermal plasma decontamination.

Industrial relevance: Non-thermal plasma decontamination shows potential but is also highly affected by the setup, and technical, biological, and food parameters. This study gives an overview of the decontamination performance that is to be expected for different matrix categories and setups, which could guide possible industrial applications. The ranking of the most important parameters to affect decontamination efficacy could be used for the optimization of these applications.

1. Introduction

Food safety accounts annually for 33 million disability-adjusted life years (DALY) and 420,000 deaths, globally (WHO, 2015). Additionally, a lot of food spoils and is wasted. In Europe, 186 Mt. CO₂-eq, 1.7 Mt. SO₂-eq, and 0.7 Mt. PO₄-eq can be attributed to food waste which means that food waste is responsible for 15% of the total climate impacts of the entire food supply chain (Scherhauser et al., 2018), and posing major challenges to ending global hunger and malnutrition (FAO, 2023). To enhance food safety and reduce food spoilage, various methods have been proposed in the past to preserve food, and thermal processing and food additives prevailed in the food industry. However, some food additives face consumer acceptance issues (Bearth et al., 2014), while others can affect the organoleptic characteristics of food. The latter stands true also for thermal processing, where for certain applications the thermal effects are not desirable (e.g., fresh produce). Along with the trends toward the application of sustainable food processing

technologies, the development of non-thermal processing methods such as non-thermal plasma (NTP) has emerged.

Plasma is a partially or fully ionized gas that can be considered the fourth state of matter with the highest energy level followed by gas, liquid, and solid. The categorization of thermal and non-thermal is based on the relationship of electrons' temperature with the temperature of ions, neutral molecules, and atoms. When these temperatures are almost the same, then the plasma is categorized as thermal, while when these are different it is categorized as non-thermal. In the latter case, the electrons can reach temperatures up to 10,000 °C (Liao et al., 2017; Scholtz et al., 2015). However, this is not the overall gas (plasma) temperature which remains below 70 °C (Schnabel et al., 2021) and cools down rapidly after its production due to its gaseous state. Possible mechanisms of microbial inactivation through NTP include DNA damage by UV radiation, lipid oxidation, protein modulation, apoptosis, electrostatic disruption, and electroporation (Liao et al., 2017). The different devices, the ambient conditions, and the mode of treatment (i.

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e., direct or indirect) can affect the production and stability (i.e., concentration, life cycle) of the reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) present in the plasma gas. Examples of indirect treatment include applications where the plasma gas is produced distantly from the sample or applications related to plasma-treated water that is then used to decontaminate the sample. The NTP devices that are described in the literature are dielectric barrier discharge (DBD), atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ), inductively-coupled plasma (ICP), gliding arc discharge (GAD), point-to-plate (PTP), corona discharge (CD), glow discharge (GD), surface barrier discharge (SBD), and surface microdischarge (SMD). Additional categorization methods exist based on the type of source (i.e., microwave plasma source (MPS), radio-frequency (RF)), the pressure (i.e., low pressure, atmospheric pressure), and the discharge type (i.e., filamentary, diffuse). Several studies have used machine learning for more efficient screening in systematic reviews (Ferdinands et al., 2023; Miwa et al., 2014), but also in the non-thermal plasma domain. Some of these studies aimed to predict the best non-thermal plasma parameters' combinations for seed priming (Shelar et al., 2022), or to predict the microbial inactivation of plasma-activated liquids for biomedical applications (Özdemir et al., 2023), and for real-time plasma diagnostics (Bonzanini et al., 2022).

Our study used active learning for the retrieval of relevant NTP studies and investigated the overall differences in the decontamination efficacy of ten different setups. Then, the concept of dissipated power per plasma volume was selected as a basis to prioritize and rank the parameters that affected the decontamination efficacy of NTP using a DBD setup through conventional and machine learning approaches.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data collection

The data were collected using five databases, namely, Scopus, Web of Science, SciFinder, Food Science and Technology (FSTA), and CAB abstracts. Three sets of keywords were used, one for plasma, one for inactivation/decontamination, and one for the microbial species of interest (Supplementary A). The microorganisms of interest were *Escherichia coli* (including total coliform counts), *Listeria* spp., *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (including total yeast counts), lactic acid bacteria, and *Bacillus* spp. These microorganisms were selected as a broad set of representatives of typical pathogenic or spoilage Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, spore formers, and yeasts. Each search was performed independently for each microbial genus, before merging, and the duplicates were removed. The data screening was conducted in two steps. For the first step, the studies were screened based on the information on the type of plasma device, achieved microbial inactivation $>0.5 \log_{10}$ reduction, and reported power expression such as applied, forward, reverse, reflected, active, apparent, operating, generating, discharge, dissociated, transferred, input, or dissipated power. The threshold of $0.5 \log_{10}$ reduction was selected because the inherent uncertainty of the measurement below this level is highly affected by the detection limit of the method and could mean that there was no actual inactivation. For the second step, the studies were screened in detail for one specific plasma device setup, namely, the DBD setup, and expressions of input or dissipated power, electrodes' dimensions, and distance between the electrodes were compiled. The rationale behind this was a first investigation of the individual studies that demonstrated that the different plasma setups induce a high variation of different parameters, that were not consistently reported. For NTP, a defining parameter equivalent to temperature for thermal processing and pressure for high-pressure processing could not be easily found. Multiple expressions of power exist in literature such as transferred, active, applied, and apparent power, which cannot be compared with certainty, as well as different approaches for estimating the RONS either in the sample or in the plasma gas, different analytical methods, and different chemical components involved. Parameters such as voltage and frequency, although

often reported in the literature, are not descriptive because they do not provide information regarding the waveform characteristics of the applied voltage. Furthermore, in most cases, it was not clear if the voltage reported was the peak-to-peak or the maximum voltage and if the frequency was the frequency of the powered device or the frequency related to the actual discharges. Thus, the second step of the screening procedure was performed by narrowing it down to only include DBD setups, because this setup was most frequently used in the studies, with clear expressions of power (i.e., input or dissipated power), electrodes' dimensions, and distance, to standardize the setup and compare the studies more consistently. In-package DBD setups where the powered electrode is placed inside a packaged food product were excluded due to the different approach of this setup and the difficulties in standardizing when compared to the remainder of the setups. Also, studies that reported synergistic effects when combining NTP with other technologies or substances, were excluded, except for the studies that provided the individual effect of NTP. Lastly, studies referring to plasma-treated water or plasma-activated water were excluded due to the difficulties of comparing the microbial inactivation with the remainder of the setups. The workflow of our study is illustrated in Fig. 1.

2.2. Screening with an active learning approach

In order to optimize the screening procedure, active learning was used for the second step of the screening process after narrowing down the scope of research to the DBD setup. Active learning is a subfield of machine learning in which the learning algorithm is allowed to choose the data from which it learns (Settles, 2009). This approach can work for various concepts such as speech recognition and information extraction, but in screening literature studies, the goal is to change the original order of the studies that are to be screened as relevant or irrelevant, choosing first the studies that have a higher probability of being relevant according to the previous researcher's choices (Settles, 2009; van de Schoot et al., 2021). The researcher still has full control of the screening process, since active learning only changes the order of the studies to be reviewed and does not label them as relevant or irrelevant. This approach was used and evaluated in various studies (Harrison et al., 2020; Marshall & Wallace, 2019; O'Mara-Eves et al., 2015; van de Schoot et al., 2021; Wallace et al., 2010), but, to our knowledge, not yet in the field of food microbiology. As the first step of the active learning procedure, an initial screening (prior knowledge) of some studies is conducted manually by the researcher to point out some relevant and irrelevant studies and then this knowledge is used to train machine learning algorithms. In our case, these algorithms were term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) as the extractor, Naive Bayes as the classifier, and Dynamic resampling as the data rebalancing strategy that makes the process more efficient for datasets that potentially include many irrelevant and a few relevant studies. The query strategy was set to maximum so that the algorithms put first for screening the study with the highest probability of being relevant based on the title and the abstract (van de Schoot et al., 2021). Based on the researcher's choice for this study (relevant or irrelevant) the algorithms are trained again including the new knowledge and put another study first etc. The procedure stops after reaching the stopping criterion that has to be defined by the researcher and is the number of consecutive irrelevant studies after which the process stops. This approach is assumed to save time as the number of studies to be screened is more realistic, and at the same time, it also does not make the search too precise and ensures that relevant studies are not missed (van de Schoot et al., 2021). The latter is crucial for non-thermal plasma since the term is undoubtedly broad and making it more specific for certain applications or setups can induce selection bias, already from the first step. Our total study list included 4800 studies (after removing the duplicates) for all plasma setups and *Escherichia coli* (including total coliform counts), *Listeria* spp., *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (including total yeast counts), lactic acid bacteria, and *Bacillus* spp. From the first step 2896 (of 4800) studies were randomly

Fig. 1. a: Data collection, and screening workflow. b: Overview of all data points across different setups. c: The concept of dissipated power per plasma volume. d: Exploratory data analysis and quantitative modeling workflow.

selected and screened manually (without active learning) for information on the type of plasma device, achieved microbial inactivation >0.5 \log_{10} reduction, and reported power expression. At this point 1904 (4800 minus 2896) studies were not screened yet. From the 2896 studies, that were initially screened manually, 57 were labeled as relevant and 2839 as irrelevant. To start the active learning procedure to screen the remaining 1904 studies and train the active learning algorithms for the second step, these 2896 labeled studies were used as prior knowledge to start with. The active learning procedure was performed using the ASReview LAB software (v1.2.1) (ASReview LAB developers, 2024). It should be noted that this prior knowledge can be established by using a way more limited number of studies (e.g., 10) just to “warm-up” the active learning algorithms. The “warm-up” in the context of an active learning procedure is the input of several starting data (like 10, or

in our case 2896, and not like a “seed” which is one starting value). For the second step, the 1904 studies that were not screened previously were used as input for the active learning procedure with a focus on DBD setup. The studies that were screened with active learning were 582 (from 1904), before reaching the stopping criterion of 200 consecutive irrelevant studies. From the second step of screening, 32 out of the 582 additional relevant studies were retrieved. The reviewing process with active learning is illustrated in Fig. 2. So in total, 3478 out of 4800 (2896 plus 582) studies were screened from which 89 (32 plus 57) were relevant, 3389 were irrelevant and the remaining 1322 (1904 minus 582) studies were not screened. The stopping criterion of 200 was an arbitrary choice, but was expected to be a conservative one in the manner that in this sequence of 200 studies not even one relevant study was found, suggesting that active learning successfully had put already on

Fig. 2. A visualization of the two different approaches to screening i.e., the manual screening procedure (blue line) and the screening procedure as assisted by active learning (yellow line). The random relevant studies (blue line) are the number of studies that are expected to be relevant in a random dataset during a manual screening procedure and are estimated based on a generic simulation of this procedure as provided by ASReview LAB software (v1.2.1). The relevant studies that are illustrated in the figure (yellow line) are based on our dataset. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the top of the order the relevant studies (Fig. 2). In addition to the 4800 studies, 294 *Salmonella* studies were searched, screened, and compiled retrospectively, when it was perceived that there were a lot of valuable studies available for *Salmonella* that could further assist in exploring NTP decontamination efficacy using the DBD setup. The search for *Salmonella* spp. was conducted using keywords only relevant to the DBD setup and not for all plasma setups as was done for the remainder of the microorganisms (Supplementary A). From this search, 7 more studies (in addition to the 89) were found to be relevant. In total, after the finalized screening for the inclusion of parameters in the database, 19 studies from both steps of the preliminary screening (i.e., manual or active learning assisted), were excluded because information on power or achieved reduction, or both, was incomplete. As a result, 77 studies (519 *D*-values or 517 microbial reduction entries (for two *D*-values the reductions were not reported)) were assessed qualitatively (for all setups), of which 9 studies on the DBD setup (160 *D*-values) were used for the quantitative modeling analyses (the 77 studies included in our database can be found in Supplementary B). The studies that reported the input power instead of the dissipated one, could not be utilized because the power loss can vary significantly for different DBD devices.

2.3. Overview of data points and qualitative analysis

The decontamination efficacy of the different plasma setups was evaluated using the *D*-value, which is the time needed to reduce a microbial population with a factor of 10 or $1 \log_{10}$. The *D*-values were estimated by fitting the Bigelow model (Bigelow, 1921) to the \log_{10} counts data (mean values per time point) versus time, using the software “Bioinactivation” (Garre et al., 2017), or calculated when the maximum rate of inactivation (k_{\max}) was reported (i.e., using the equation $\ln 10/k_{\max}$). When inactivation kinetics were only reported as a graph, the tool “WebPlotDigitizer” (Rohatgi, 2022) was used to extract the \log_{10} counts. It should be noted that the inactivation kinetics were also fitted using the Weibull model where possible (Mafart et al., 2002), but due to the limited number of observations in most of the NTP experiments (only 165/519 entries reported >4 observations, including the zero time point, and only 135/519 reported >5 observations), tail and shoulder effects could not be accurately estimated. Thus, the Weibull shape parameter estimates were not further used in this study but can be shared upon request. All $\log_{10}D$ values were standardized to \log_{10} min. The $\log_{10}D$ values of the different setups found in the literature were compared, namely, ICP: Inductively coupled plasma, APPJ: Atmospheric pressure plasma jet, DBD: Dielectric barrier discharge, LPDBD: Low-pressure dielectric barrier discharge, SBD: Surface barrier discharge, RFLPCP: Radiofrequency low-pressure cold plasma, CD: Corona discharge, LPMPs: Low-pressure microwave plasma source, PTP: Point-to-plate plasma, MPS: Microwave plasma source. The overview of the achieved reductions was assessed for five different matrix categories: i., solid food; ii., liquid food (treated on an abiotic surface); iii., solid medium; iv., liquid medium (treated on an abiotic surface) and, v., (dry) abiotic surface. The corresponding products for each category can be found in Supplementary Table 1.

2.4. The concept of dissipated power per plasma volume

In this research, the concept of dissipated power per plasma volume is proposed as a defining descriptor of NTP inactivation efficacy that can be easily estimated for DBD devices. This is because RONS concentrations, although directly associated with inactivation efficacy, are difficult to define (which species, where), measure (which device, which method, trained personnel) and report consistently (concentration, relative concentration, or spectrograph), making plasma diagnostics very complex. Additionally, the approach of RONS could be too specific or not include reactive species that could have an effect and are not measured accurately with the current methodology (e.g., short-lived reactive species). Thus, we used the power that is used for the crea-

tion of plasma (dissipated power, P_{dis}), divided by the volume of the plasma produced, i.e. power density (P_{dens}), as an integrated plasma descriptor. Dissipated power, was chosen, because it is a more comprehensive parameter compared to other devices' properties as the peak-to-peak voltage and frequency, as explained above. The method to estimate the dissipated power can be found in Eq. (1).

$$P_{\text{dis}} = U \cdot I \cdot \cos(\phi) \quad (\text{W}) \quad (1)$$

where U is the voltage (in volts, V), I is the current (in amperes, A), and ϕ (–) is the phase shift between current and voltage (Golda et al., 2016). Some modifications of this equation to make estimations easily applicable for some setups can be found in Golda et al. (2019).

For DBD devices this concept can be approximated using the dissipated power, divided by the powered electrode area and the distance between the powered and the ground electrode (Eq. (2)).

$$P_{\text{dens}} = \frac{P_{\text{dis}}}{A \cdot d} \quad (\text{W}/\text{cm}^3) \quad (2)$$

where A is the powered electrode area (in cm^2) and d is the distance (in cm) between the powered and ground electrode.

It should be noted that the true plasma area can be smaller than the powered electrode's area, because the effective area in which plasma is created can be smaller than the area that is defined by the electrodes' dimensions. In the same manner, the width can be smaller than the distance between the electrodes, especially as the distance increases (de Souza et al., 2016). However, these two system parameters together with the dissipated power are expected to affect most of the plasma creation and the corresponding inactivation efficacy.

2.5. Exploratory data analysis

An exploratory data analysis was conducted using Python programming language (v3.11) (Van Rossum & Drake, 2009) and the libraries “numpy” (Harris et al., 2020), “pandas” (McKinney, 2010), “seaborn” (Waskom, 2021), “matplotlib” (Hunter, 2007), “scikit” (Pedregosa et al., 2011), and “scipy” (Virtanen et al., 2020). Firstly, all the relevant power and energy expressions (dissipated power (W), dissipated power per plasma area (W/cm^2), dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3), dissipated energy (W·min), dissipated energy per plasma area ($\text{W} \cdot \text{min}/\text{cm}^2$), dissipated energy per plasma volume ($\text{W} \cdot \text{min}/\text{cm}^3$)) were separately checked for their correlation with the $\log_{10}D$ (\log_{10} min) using the Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (Supplementary Fig. 1) to evaluate which could function as an integrated plasma descriptor. Then the other numerical and categorical variables that were included in the database for the DBD studies were evaluated, namely, the numerical variables peak-to-peak voltage (kV), frequency (kHz), relative humidity (%), product temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) after treatment, sample area (cm^2), pH (–), and the categorical variables ground electrode shape (circular plate, rectangle), ground electrode material (copper, stainless steel), upper electrode shape (circular plate, rectangle), upper electrode material (copper, stainless steel), dominant working gas (air, Ar, He, N_2 , $\text{N}_2:\text{O}_2$), matrix category, food (yes, no), microbial genus (*Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Escherichia*, and *Bacillus* (no data for the non-mentioned genera)), species (*monocytogenes*, *innocua*, *enterica*, *coli*, *cereus*), strain (LMG 23775, ATCC 33090, ATCC 25922, Ampres-mutant, LMG 13305, LMG 14933, SL 1344, ATCC 13311), type of cells (vegetative, biofilm), mode of inoculation (surface, whole sample), selective recovery medium (yes, no). For the categorical variables, the Kruskal-Wallis H test (non-parametric alternative to one-way ANOVA) was used to test if there are statistically significant differences between the different groups' $\log_{10}D$ median value for each categorical variable. The Kruskal-Wallis H test provides two outputs, the H-statistic (the higher, the greater the differences) and the *p*-value, to see if the differences between the subgroups are statistically significant. Cramér's V was also performed as a measure of association between the categorical

variables to test if the categorical variables are associated with each other. Cramer's V provides the φ_c value which is the intercorrelation coefficient and can take values from 0 (no association) to 1 (perfect association). The summaries of statistics and violin plots were also used in this case to explore potential parameters affecting the $\log_{10}D$.

2.6. Quantitative modeling

2.6.1. Data splitting and scaling of numerical variables

Unless mentioned differently, the data were first split into a training and a test set. This step was implemented before scaling to avoid data leakage (from the training to the test set during the scaling step) (Lones, 2021). The test set was set to 20% of the full dataset ($n_{\text{training}} = 128$, $n_{\text{test}} = 32$). The training and test sets were selected randomly using the "random_state" function (pseudo-random numbers) of the "scikit" library (Pedregosa et al., 2011). The numerical variables of the training set were then scaled using the standard score (z) of a sample value (x) with mean (u) and standard deviation (s), and the estimated mean and standard deviation of each of the variables were used for scaling also the test data (Eq. (3)).

$$z = \frac{(x - u)}{s} \quad (3)$$

Subtracting the mean from a sample value typically improves the interpretation of main effects in the presence of interactions, while dividing by the standard deviation puts all variables on a common scale (Gelman, 2008). After scaling, the variable coefficients indicate the expected difference in the dependent variable for each standard deviation change in the variable's value. This was done because the scale i.e., the range of values of the numerical variables was varying significantly. For example, the dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3) values ranged from $0.02 W/cm^3$ to $2 W/cm^3$, whereas the peak-to-peak voltage (V) ranged from 4.5 kV to 25 kV, and the relative humidity from 0% to 80%. With scaling the statistical significance of the variables does not change i.e., the p -values of the predictors' set will remain the same, but the interpretation and comparison of the relative importance (comparing the coefficients instead of their p -value) is improved (Schielzeth, 2010).

2.6.2. Imputation strategies

A selected set of values for some studies was imputed so as not to have missing values for the modeling part. For the relative humidity and pH, the imputation strategy was quite straightforward. For the cases with missing information, the relative humidity was assumed to be 50% (the average of 40–60% which is assumed to be a common relative humidity range at room temperature), whilst the pH of abiotic surfaces was assumed to be 7 (including the eggshells' surface). The pH of Trypticase Soy Broth with Yeast Extract was assumed to be 7.3 (US FDA, 1998), with or without the addition of xanthan gum. For the sample area, a more complex approach was implemented. The approach was to use k -nearest neighbor (k -NN). The k -NN is a method that tries to classify an unknown sample based on the known classification of its neighbors (Mucherino et al., 2009). In our case, to predict the missing values of the sample area we used the matrix category, the sample size, and the research team (on the assumption that research teams often work with the same product dimensions based on their equipment) neighbor values to estimate the non-reported sample area based on the value of the sample area that the neighbor values of the aforementioned parameters were pointing to. The number of neighbors to be used was set at 8. This is an arbitrary choice that in our case was based on the density plot that compared the distribution of the original values with the imputed ones. This number of neighbors yielded the best overlap between the two distributions. (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The density results of the imputation strategy applied to the sample area. The density of the reported sample area is colored with purple, whereas the imputed one is colored with green. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2.6.3. Multiple linear regression and regularization techniques

The approach of multiple linear regression (MLR) was implemented due to its simplicity and its high interpretability. This approach was performed to the full dataset ($n = 160$), as well as to the training dataset used for the machine learning approaches (80% i.e., $n_{\text{train}} = 128$), to compare the different methods. Ordinary least squares regression was used for this step using backward elimination with a threshold of p -value = 0.05. The dependent variable was the $\log_{10}D$ ($\log_{10} \text{min}$) and the potential predictors were, as determined by the exploratory data analysis, the dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3), the peak-to-peak voltage (kV), the relative humidity (%), the sample area (cm^2), the pH (–), the upper electrode shape (circular plate, rectangle), the upper electrode material (copper, stainless steel), the matrix category (solid medium, liquid medium, abiotic surface), and the microbial genus (*Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Escherichia*). The categories that are not mentioned here, i.e., solid and liquid foods, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and yeasts, lactic acid bacteria, and coliforms were not included in the dataset used for the regression because they could not meet the criteria set i.e., DBD setup, achieved microbial inactivation $>0.5 \log_{10}$ reduction, and reported dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3) parameters. For *Bacillus cereus*, there was only one entry (additional to the 160) that met the criteria and thus it was excluded. The categorical variables were converted to dummy variables (0,1) and the first category of each variable, which was most often reported in the studies, was set as the base to avoid the dummy variable trap which would lead to multicollinearity between the dummy variables (Suits, 1957), although the effect of the base selection for each category was evaluated. In an attempt to further improve variable selection while retaining interpretability, regularization techniques were applied, as a different approach to backward elimination. Regularization is a technique used in statistics to help deal with multicollinearity and predictors' selection, through two main steps: parameter approximations' construction, and approximation selection based on bias-variance trade-off (Bickel et al., 2006), instead of relying on the p -value of each independent variable as it is done with backward elimination. Thus, lasso (Tibshirani, 1996), ridge (Hoerl & Kennard, 1970), and elastic net (Zou & Hastie, 2005) were used for their ability to perform regularization L1 (Supplementary C, eq. S1), L2 (Supplementary C, eq. S2), or both (Supplementary C, eq. S3), respectively. In general, ridge performs better than lasso for datasets with a substantial

number of (collinear) variables, but of the two only lasso can shrink some variables' coefficients to 0, and thus perform variable selection (Neto et al., 2014), and elastic net combines both approaches. As with every machine learning concept, there are two different parameter categories involved i.e., the ones that can be initialized and updated through the data learning process (i.e., model parameters) and the ones that cannot be directly estimated from data learning and must be set before training because they define the model architecture (i.e., hyperparameters) (Yang & Shami, 2020). The model parameters in this case are the intercept and the coefficients of the multiple linear regression model, while the hyperparameters are constants that control the regularization penalties from which the model architecture is defined (the starting point from which the "machine" starts to "learn") and the iterative learning process starts to minimize the least squares penalty. The hyperparameter selection tuning is an arbitrary choice that involves trial-error simulations, using the training set. In order to make this approach more systematic the hyperparameter tuning was conducted using Optuna which is a software that uses sampling algorithms to find more promising hyperparameters based on past trial results and pruning algorithms to eliminate the less promising ones (Akiba et al., 2019). In our case, we split the training set into 5 and in each iteration, the four parts were used to train the model and the one was used to validate it. The procedure using Optuna continues for 5000 iterations to find the optimal combination that yields the best model fit with the lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

2.6.4. Machine learning approaches

To unveil more complex relationships between the dependent and the independent variables, three machine learning algorithms were tested, namely, random forests, extreme gradient boosting, support vector machines, and artificial neural networks. Random forests are a combination of tree predictors such that each decision tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently and with the same distribution for all trees in the forest (Breiman, 2001). Each decision tree consists of the root node, internal nodes, leaf nodes, and branches. The root node is the initial decision after which the data is split. The internal nodes are the points where the data is split further, and the leaf nodes are the nodes where the data cannot be split any further. The branches are the links between the nodes that represent the outcome of each test. The hyperparameters that were chosen for tuning for our case were the number of trees in the forest, the maximum depth of each tree, the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node, and the minimum number of samples required to be a leaf node. Gradient boosting, as random forests, is also a form of ensemble learning i.e., using a set of hypotheses instead of one to choose a set of weights to construct the "voted" classifier (or regressor) (Dietterich, 2002). This means that also for this case we compose our model based on multiple decision trees. The difference is that the approach of gradient boosting is sequential and can formulate additive expansions for any fitting criterion (Friedman, 2001). The extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) algorithm was used with tree booster, where each new tree attempts to correct the errors made by the previous ones. The hyperparameters that were chosen for tuning were the number of gradient-boosting trees, the maximum depth of each tree (from the root to the leaf node), the learning rate (shrinkage factor) that scales the contribution of each tree corrections to the next one to avoid overfitting, and the subsample ratio of the instances used for training before growing each tree that also helps to avoid overfitting (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). Support vector machines (SVM) use the SV algorithm that regulates the capacity by considering the function corresponding to the hyperplane that separates, according to the labels, the given training data and it is maximally distant from them (Boser et al., 1992; Cristianini & Ricci, 2016; Hearst et al., 1998). As such, SVM tries to find a decision boundary (i.e., hyperplane) that separates distinctly different data points into categories. It focuses on maximizing the distance (margin) between the data points of each category and the decision boundary, ensuring a clear separation

of the data points into categories. The hyperparameters that were chosen for tuning were the regularization parameter (C), the epsilon tube, and the kernel coefficient. The regularization parameter C controls the balance between minimizing the misclassification and maximizing the margin between categories. The epsilon tube refers to a margin of tolerance within which some prediction errors are not penalized, to avoid overfitting i.e., a larger tube allows more errors, and a lower forces to a higher sensitivity which may lead to overfitting. (Chang & Lin, 2011). Lastly, the kernel coefficient chooses the way to transform the data in higher dimensional space to make it possible to perform linear separation, when the original data are not linearly separable. Artificial neural networks simulate networks of multiple interconnected building blocks called model neurons. Each model neuron receives input data, assigns a weight factor to each input, and then sums the weighted inputs. This sum is then passed through an activation function which converts it to a modified output. For instance, an activation function can be used to introduce non-linearity to the model enabling the network to learn complex patterns in the data. The output from the activation function is then passed to the next layer and the process is repeated for multiple layers and data combinations. Back-propagation is implemented in every pass from the input to the output data to correct the weight factors in each layer. This is done based on the loss function change concerning each weight value in the network (Krogh, 2008). In this study, the number of model neurons in the input layer corresponded to the number of parameters of the database, and each row of the database constituted the input data. Each model neuron in one layer was connected to every model neuron in the next layer. This connection between the layers was made possible by assigning different weight factors for each parameter's value, summing up the weighted values for all parameters, and passing them to the next layer through an activation function. The activation function used was the activation function rectifier linear activation which converts the non-positive sums of the inputs to 0 and the positive ones to their actual value, essentially creating a piecewise linear function with two linear pieces (Goodfellow et al., 2016). The loss function that was used in this study for the back-propagation step was the mean square error. The hyperparameters that were chosen for tuning were the number of hidden layers (the layers between the input and the output layers), the number of model neurons on each hidden layer, the dropout rate which selects a fraction of the model neurons not to be included in every pass (to avoid overfitting), and the learning rate which controls how much the weight factors change in each pass. All the above machine learning approaches have a lot more hyperparameters that can be tuned for better results, but given the limited number of data points ($n = 160$), this was unnecessary. The hyperparameters that were not tuned, were set to their default values, as determined by the "Scikit-learn" software that was used for random forests, XGBoost, and SVM (Pedregosa et al., 2011). For neural networks, the "TensorFlow" software was used (Abadi et al., 2015). For the hyperparameters that were tuned, Optuna (Akiba et al., 2019) was used for all machine learning approaches, as explained in Section 2.6.3. For the interpretation of the parameters that contribute the most to the machine learning models, the Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) approach was followed and the Shapley values were estimated for each independent variable. The SHAP framework is based on the game theory and identifies the class of additive feature importance methods and shows that there is a unique solution in this class that adheres to desirable properties (Lundberg & Lee, 2017). In a typical SHAP summary plot, each dot represents the SHAP value for each parameter for each data point of the test set which means that the number of dots matches the number of the data points in the test set. The SHAP value scale (x-axis) is relative and centered around 0 and the dots that are on the right side push the dependent variable to positive correlations with the independent variable (higher $\log_{10}D$), whereas the dots on the left push it to the negative correlations with the independent variable (lower $\log_{10}D$). The variables' colors are based on the actual value of each parameter i.e., when the colour is leaning to red then this corresponds to the data points that have higher values of this parameter,

while blue corresponds to lower values of this parameter. If the red dots of a parameter are scattered on the left side and the blue dots are scattered on the right side this could imply a negative correlation of the independent variable with the dependent variable, whereas when the blue dots of a parameter are on the left side, and the red dots are on the right side, this could imply a positive correlation. If the red or blue data points or both are scattered on both sides, then this could imply that the correlation exists but the positive or negative effect is condition-dependent. If both dots are centered around 0 (low mean absolute SHAP value) this could imply that the parameter has low or no contribution to the model's output. For dummy variables, there are only two possible outcomes (colors), where red corresponds to the presence of the effect, and blue to the absence of the effect (base), but their interpretation is analogous; for instance, red dots on the left side could imply a negative correlation, and so forth.

3. Results

3.1. Overview of D -value entries for all setups

The $\log_{10}D$ values obtained for the different NTP setups are shown in Fig. 4 and are in line with Baier et al. (2013), who reported that there is significant variation between the different types of plasma sources and their mode of application. Our results showed that the APPJ was the setup with the lowest median D -value (0.5 min), and LPDPB had the highest median D -value (15 min). Differences in the extent of variability also exist, for instance, in the $\log_{10}D$ of the LPDPB setup where the variability was higher than LPMPs despite the more data points of the latter. It should be noted that the reliability of these estimates is not the same for all setups since the number of data points differs for the different plasma setups (Fig. 4).

The overview of the microbial reductions achieved with NTP against various microorganisms and matrices is shown in Table 1. For lactic acid bacteria, there were no studies in the literature that met the eligibility criteria (information on the type of plasma device, achieved microbial inactivation $>0.5 \log_{10}$ reduction, and reported power expression). This table can serve as a map of what decontamination is to be expected in general for most NTP setups. A huge variation between the different

combinations of matrix-microorganism can be observed with the median reduction using NTP ranging from 1.1 to 7.9 \log_{10} . This variation entails the effect of the setup as well as other effects such as the specific matrix (e.g., the particular food product), the power, and the processing time used, but it is informative in terms of answering simple questions regarding NTP decontamination efficacy according to the current literature, without specific criteria. It should be noted that these values were most probably an underestimation of the efficacy since in experiments where NTP processing led to microbial counts below the detection limit, the previous time-point was used. However, considering also the inactivation entries that led to microbial counts below the detection limit using only the entries with an initial inoculum of $\geq 5 \log_{10}$, 20.1% (71 of 352) of the total entries led to an inactivation $\geq 5 \log_{10}$ or below the detection limit with entries for all microorganisms and matrix categories and with DBD, APPJ, ICP, PTP and SBD setups (data not shown).

From a modeling perspective, the most important issue in assessing the sources of variability within each setup was the lack of a parameter present in all studies, that is equivalent for example to temperature for thermal processing or pressure for high-pressure processing to standardize the results. We focused on the DBD setup because according to the findings of this study (Fig. 4) and previous research (Asl et al., 2022; Liao et al., 2017), it is the most common setup with the most data reported on. Atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) was the second most frequent setup in our database. It should be noted that DBD offers a short but wide discharge in which the sample is part of it, whereas the APPJ can treat a sample from a longer distance (the sample is not part of the discharge), but in a smaller area (Yan et al., 2016). DBD devices can produce stable and uniform NTP while working at relatively low temperatures under atmospheric pressure (Liao et al., 2017). Additionally, for the DBD setup, it was easier to estimate the plasma volume and thus the dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3). This concept is not so easily transferable to APPJ or other setups.

3.2. Exploratory data analysis for DBD

3.2.1. Power expression selection and evaluation

Moving to the DBD setup, 160 D -values were estimated that reported all the required power density equation components (dissipated power,

Fig. 4. Overview of all D -values obtained for different plasma setups. APPJ: Atmospheric pressure plasma jet (median D -value = 0.54 min), CD: Corona discharge (median D -value = 1.0 min), SBD: Surface barrier discharge (median D -value = 1.3 min), DBD: Dielectric barrier discharge (median D -value = 1.8 min), ICP: Inductively coupled plasma (median D -value = 1.9 min), PTP: Point-to-plate plasma (median D -value = 3.4 min), MPS: Microwave plasma source (median D -value = 3.9 min), LPMPs: Low-pressure microwave plasma source (median D -value = 5.0 min), RFLPCP: Radiofrequency low-pressure cold plasma (median D -value = 8.8 min), LPDPB: Low-pressure Dielectric barrier discharge (median D -value = 14.9 min). The medians of each group are represented with a black dot. The n represents the number of D -values for each type of equipment and the s represents the corresponding number of studies. The violin plots are ordered based on the median $\log_{10}D$ for each type of equipment.

Table 1
Overview of microbial log₁₀ reductions across different matrix categories.

Matrix category	<i>Listeria</i> spp. ^{a, b}	<i>Salmonella</i> spp. ^{a, b}	<i>Bacillus</i> spp. ^{a, c}	Coliforms ^a	Yeasts ^a
solid food	1.7, 2.0 ± 1.3 (n = 39)	7.9, 7.9 (n = 1)	1.7, 2.2 ± 1.3 (n = 12)	1.5, 1.9 ± 1.3 (n = 67)	2.4, 2.4 ± 1.0 (n = 6)
liquid food	5.4, 4.4 ± 1.7 (n = 3)	–	5.2, 4.7 ± 0.9 (n = 3)	3.4, 3.2 ± 1.1 (n = 9)	1.1, 1.1 ± 0.7 (n = 2)
solid medium	1.7, 2.0 ± 1.5 (n = 25)	1.5, 1.6 ± 0.6 (n = 14)	–	3.5, 3.4 ± 1.2 (n = 22)	–
liquid medium	1.4, 2.6 ± 2.7 (n = 18)	2.2, 2.0 ± 0.7 (n = 14)	3.6, 3.4 ± 1.5 (n = 14)	4.5, 4.4 ± 1.4 (n = 40)	3.9, 3.7 ± 2.4 (n = 24)
abiotic surface	1.9, 2.1 ± 1.0 (n = 69)	2.2, 2.4 ± 1.0 (n = 51)	4.0, 3.9 ± 1.2 (n = 35)	2.7, 2.5 ± 1.3 (n = 46)	2.6, 3.1 ± 1.0 (n = 3)
Total	154	80	64	184	35

^a The values correspond to the reductions above the detection limit and are reported as median, mean ± SD.

^b For *Listeria* spp. and *Salmonella* spp. both vegetative and biofilm cells are reported.

^c For *Bacillus* spp. both vegetative and spore cells are reported.

electrodes' dimensions, distance between the electrodes) (Eq. (2)) concerning *Listeria* spp., *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli*. For yeasts, lactic acid bacteria, and coliforms (different than *E. coli*) no entries were reporting the aforementioned parameters. The entries for *Listeria* spp., *Salmonella enterica*, and *Escherichia coli* were 70, 79, and 11, respectively. The corresponding products for each category can be found in Supplementary Table 2. The exploratory data analysis indicated that from the power- and energy-related expressions, the most negatively correlated (with the log₁₀D (log₁₀ min)) were the dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm³) and the dissipated power per plasma area (W/cm²) with the highest Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (Supplementary Fig. 1). The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was –0.16 for both expressions which was rather low but still the highest among the power expressions. From the two expressions, the dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm³) was selected, because it incorporates one more parameter that is crucial for DBD i.e., the electrodes' distance, in a rational and parsimonious way (de Souza et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2004).

3.2.2. Variable selection

Based on the exploratory data analysis, from the numerical variables, the product temperature (°C) was excluded based on the scatterplot with the log₁₀D (log₁₀ min) and the low Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (Supplementary Fig. 2). The peak-to-peak voltage was considered for the next steps even though it showed a low Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, because of a slight trend in its scatterplot with the log₁₀D, whereas the frequency (kHz) was not considered because no trend could be observed in its scatterplot (Supplementary Fig. 3). The dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm³), sample area (cm²), relative humidity (%), peak-to-peak voltage (kV), and pH (–) were considered for the imputation and modeling steps. It should be noted that the RONS, although important, were not reported in any of these entries, neither as a whole nor as individual chemical compounds. Moving to the categorical variables, from the Kruskal-Wallis H-test and the violin plots, dominant working gas, type of cells, food (yes, no), and selective recovery medium (yes, no) did not seem to have a significant influence (both statistically and visually) on the log₁₀D (log₁₀ min). From the results of Cramér's V, the shape and material of the ground and

upper electrodes were intercorrelated with intercorrelation coefficient $\rho_c > 0.95$ respectively, hence, the upper electrode shape and the upper electrode material were selected as categorical variables, because the upper electrode is also the powered one. The microbial genus was intercorrelated with the species ($\rho_c = 0.99$) and the strain ($\rho_c = 0.98$) and thus only the microbial genus was used because it has fewer categories (i.e., fewer dummy variables) and thus sets a more parsimonious basis. The mode of inoculation was intercorrelated with the matrix category ($\rho_c = 0.99$) and thus only the matrix category was used. To sum up, from the numerical variables, dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm³), sample area (cm²), relative humidity (%), peak-to-peak voltage (kV), and pH were considered, and from the categorical variables, upper electrode shape, upper electrode material, matrix category, and microbial genus were considered as potential predictors for the next steps, respectively. These potential predictors were selected to be imputed where needed so as not to have missing values for the modeling part. From the numerical variables, sample area, relative humidity, and pH had 77, 155, and 84, missing values, respectively. From the categorical variables, only the upper electrode material had 149 missing values but was not imputed, and therefore excluded from the next steps, because no possible strategy could be established. All other variables were imputed as explained in Section 2.6.2.

3.3. Multiple linear regression

Multiple linear regression was performed for the parameters power density (W/cm³), sample area (cm²), upper electrode shape, matrix category, pH, microbial genus, peak-to-peak voltage (kV), and relative humidity (%). The upper electrode shape of the circular plate (one of the two categories), the matrix category of the abiotic surface (one of the three categories), and the microbial genus of *Salmonella* (one of the three categories) were the most frequent categories and were set as the base for all regression analyses. The categorical variables with three categories (microbial species, matrix category) were evaluated per category, and the effect of base selection on the significance evaluation of the variables was checked through separate trials. The order of the variable coefficients changed as a result of scaling all numerical variable values using Eq. (3) (Table 2), which underlined the need for scaling for better

Table 2

The effect of scaling in the order of the coefficients using all data points (n = 160) and multiple linear regression with backward elimination. The coefficients are ordered based on the absolute coefficient values with scaling. The R² of the multiple linear regression model with or without scaling was 0.342.

Parameters	Coefficients with scaling	SE	Coefficients without scaling	SE	p-value
Upper electrode shape of rectangle	–1.31	0.36	–1.31	0.36	< 0.001
Matrix category of liquid medium	0.47	0.10	0.47	0.10	< 0.001
Sample area (cm ²)	–0.34	0.09	–0.07	0.02	< 0.001
Power density (W/cm ³)	–0.31	0.05	–1.52	0.23	< 0.001
Microbial genus of <i>Listeria</i>	–0.16	0.07	–0.16	0.07	0.022
pH	–0.07	0.03	–0.12	0.06	0.033
Peak-to-peak voltage (kV)	–	–	–	–	> 0.05
Matrix category of solid medium	–	–	–	–	> 0.05
Relative humidity (%)	–	–	–	–	> 0.05
Microbial genus of <i>Escherichia</i>	–	–	–	–	> 0.05
Intercept	0.33	0.06	2.89	0.58	< 0.001

Fig. 5. Overview of the $\log_{10}D$ values of the DBD setup that was used for modeling purposes. The regression lines of the $\log_{10}D$ (\log_{10} min) are fitted as a linear function of dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3) for each matrix category.

insights into the relative importance based on the coefficients. The mean and the standard deviation used for scaling the numerical variables can be found in Supplementary Table 3. Using all data points ($n = 160$) (Fig. 5) and backward elimination using scaled variables, the peak-to-peak voltage, and the relative humidity were excluded as non-significant variables (Table 2). It should be noted that the *Bacillus* entry that was excluded because it was the only one for this microbial genus (although it matched the eligibility criteria, see section 2.6.3) had the same power density level as the *E. coli* at $2 W/cm^3$ (Fig. 5). In addition, the model was tested by excluding the *E. coli* entry at $2 W/cm^3$ and the effect of power density was still prominent. The results suggested that the upper electrode shape, the matrix category, the sample area, and the power density significantly affected the $\log_{10}D$, next to the pH and the microbial genus, with the latter two variables being just significant. The microbial genus of *Listeria* was significantly different from *Salmonella*, while *Escherichia* was not significant for the model's output. For the matrix category, the matrix category of the liquid medium was significantly different from both the abiotic surface and the solid medium, whereas the abiotic surface and the solid medium were not significantly different from each other.

When we split the data, to consistently compare the multiple linear regression results with the machine learning approaches, in training and test i.e., 80:20 ($n_{train} = 128$, $n_{test} = 32$), then the coefficients with scaling were slightly different but with the same order as with the full dataset (Fig. 6). Then, elastic net was selected to perform the multiple linear regression with regularization due to its ability to penalize the variables' coefficients (reduce their value) in case of multicollinearity and even shrink them to zero (exclusion of the variable from the model), in case needed. This approach is more beneficial for datasets with a lot of

variables but not so many observations and deals with the predictor selection in a different way than using the p -values of the coefficients in the elimination procedure (backward elimination). For the optimal combination of the hyperparameter α and ρ , Optuna was used as explained in Section 2.6.3. The optimal hyperparameter α and ρ were found 0.0005 and 0.00002, respectively. The low α indicated that a minimal regularization was applied, while the low ρ indicated that from the two components of the elastic net regularization equation (i.e., lasso and ridge), the ridge component was mostly used (Supplementary C, eq. S3). All variables were selected from the regression as predictors and none of them was shrunk to 0, and the R^2 on the training and test dataset were 0.40 and 0.07, respectively while the RMSE on the test dataset was $0.46 \log_{10}$ min. Since the elastic net did not improve the model's performance much as the R^2 only slightly increased (from 0.38 (for the training dataset) to 0.40), we used multiple linear regression with backward elimination (with scaling and data split in training and test) as the basis for comparing the multiple linear regression with the machine learning approaches.

3.4. Machine learning approaches

To unveil more complex relationships between the dependent and the independent variables, random forests, eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), support vector machines (SVM), and neural networks were used. Based on cross-validation in the training set, Optuna used 5000 iterations to determine the combination of hyperparameters with the lowest RMSE. The best-fitted model was with the use of the XGBoost algorithm (R^2 on test dataset = 0.71) followed closely by random forests (R^2 on test dataset = 0.70) and then SVM (R^2 on test dataset = 0.65), and

Fig. 6. The output of multiple linear regression and the SHAP values of the XGBoost model using the scaled dataset split in training and test. In multiple linear regression, the parameters with p -value > 0.05 were excluded from the model (model R^2 was 0.384). In the XGBoost model that is visualized through the SHAP values, each dot represents the SHAP value for each parameter for each data point of the test set. The SHAP value scale is relative and centered around 0 and the dots that are on the right side push the $\log_{10}D$ ($\log_{10} \min$) to higher values, whereas the dots on the left push it to the lower values. The parameters are ordered based on the mean absolute SHAP value. The parameters' colors are based on the actual value of each parameter i.e., when the colour is leaning to red then this corresponds to the data points that have higher values of this parameter, while blue corresponds to lower values of this parameter. For dummy variables, red corresponds to the presence of the effect, and blue to the absence of the effect. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

neural networks (R^2 on test dataset = 0.34). Therefore, the XGBoost model was used for further comparison with multiple linear regression. The corresponding hyperparameters for XGBoost were: number of estimators (the number of gradient-boosted trees) = 69, maximum depth (the maximum depth of each tree) = 3, learning rate (the shrinkage factor of new trees added to the model) = 0.29, and subsample (the fraction of samples to be used for fitting each tree) = 0.63. The test dataset was used for interpretations in all machine learning approaches. Based on the mean absolute SHAP values in the test dataset (Fig. 6), the power density, the sample area, and the matrix category of liquid medium were in the top five parameters with the highest effect on the $\log_{10}D$, which were also the highly significant parameters of the multiple linear regression. The pH and the microbial genus of *Listeria* which were just significant with the multiple linear regression, were the remaining two of the top five based on the mean absolute SHAP values of the XGBoost model. The microbial genus of *Listeria* had lower $\log_{10}D$ values than *Salmonella*, as indicated by the majority of the red data points scattered on the left side, and the blue data points on the right side of the SHAP figure. The microbial genus of *Escherichia* had a minimal contribution to the model with all data points scattered around zero. For the matrix category of liquid medium, the red dots on the right side and the blue data points on the left side indicated that the matrix category of liquid medium had higher $\log_{10}D$ values than the abiotic surface (in accordance with the positive coefficient of multiple linear regression), while the matrix category of solid medium had a minimal contribution to the model with all points scattered on the left side and close to zero. The insignificant variables of the multiple linear regression were also the variables with the lowest mean absolute SHAP values of the XGBoost model i.e., peak-to-peak voltage (kV), and relative humidity (Fig. 6). The direction of the effect on the efficacy (positive or negative) was also consistent (i.e., the negative correlation coefficients of multiple linear regression matched with the red dots on the left side of the SHAP figure) except for the effect of sample area, where the negative coefficient of multiple linear regression was “translated” to red dots in both sides of the SHAP figure, pushing the model to either a positive or negative direction depending on the context which occurs, and not in a uniform way in the whole dataset. The main difference between the two methods was regarding the effect of the upper electrode shape which was highly significant based on multiple linear regression analysis, but with almost

zero contribution to the XGBoost model. This could be due to the huge differences in the frequency of the two shapes i.e., 145 data points for the circular plate shape and 15 data points for the rectangle shape, which can induce uncertainty in the parameter estimate (Supplementary Fig. 4). Using the hyperparameters determined with Optuna, a reduced model with only the 5 parameters with the highest mean absolute SHAP values, i.e., power density, microbial genus of *Listeria*, sample area, pH, and the matrix category of liquid medium, was tested. In this case, the power density was the most important factor with a mean absolute SHAP value of 0.2, whereas the rest of the parameters were scattered around 0.1. The direction of the effect on the efficacy was the same as with the full model. Combining the results of MLR and XGBoost, it can be concluded that power density and matrix category are important parameters affecting the $\log_{10}D$, followed by microbial genus and pH, while peak-to-peak voltage and relative humidity have lower importance. The impact of sample area and electrode shape could not be well defined based on the current data set. The fact that the XGBoost SHAP values were estimated from the test data, while the linear coefficients were obtained based on the training data, and still align to mostly the same ranking of parameters makes the conclusions more robust.

4. Discussion

Active learning demonstrated to be a useful tool for making the literature screening more efficient, in terms of time but also for exploring a broad domain where keywords cannot make the search specific enough (e.g., plasma). The selection of the stopping criterion for this study was based on pragmatic criteria that fit the purpose of having the overview of the technology's literature before narrowing it down to the DBD setup (Callaghan & Müller-Hansen, 2020). However, a more complex approach for its optimal selection such as statistical stopping criteria should also be considered for fully systematic literature reviews (Callaghan & Müller-Hansen, 2020).

The different setups of NTP showed huge variations in the decontamination efficacy. As mentioned in previous research, different plasma systems generate different plasmas with different reactive plasma cocktails that in general cannot be compared (Niquet et al., 2018; Shimizu et al., 2017). Based on the data collected, the top 50% of setups (i.e., 5 out of 10) in terms of decontamination efficacy were APPJ, CD, SBD, DBD, and ICP with a median D -value below 2 min for all cases. The

lowest 50% had median *D*-values higher than 3 min for all cases reaching up to 15 min for the case of LPDBD (Fig. 4). As mentioned, some parameters and the lack of data for some setups could change this outcome but at the same time, our research during the first step was performed with simple criteria and without restrictions to any particular setup.

The dissipated power was selected as an accurate enough basis since RONS are rarely reported in the literature and the results are not easily comparable. Not only power was rarely reported in the literature, but the terminology was also not consistent in the studies, because power was reported as applied, forward, reverse, reflected, active, apparent, operating, generating, discharge, dissociated, transferred, input, or dissipated power and also their mean, min, and max values or terms like power density without further explanation. Hence, dissipated power was used for consistency reasons, because it is correlated to the inactivation efficacy according to the literature (Gabriel et al., 2016; Govaert et al., 2019) and was more often reported than the other variants e.g., discharge. It should be noted that in most of the studies, the power that is dissipated to the plasma is the same for different working gas compositions, for instance, Georgescu et al. (2017) pointed out that power dissipation in the plasma gas was the same for different working gas compositions (Georgescu et al., 2017). However, Govaert et al. (2019) reported a disparity in the power that is dissipated to the plasma when using different working gas compositions (Govaert et al., 2019).

The concept of dissipated power per plasma volume that is established in the current study, although easily approximated for DBD devices using the dissipated power, electrodes' dimensions, and the distance between them, can be more challenging to apply for other setups such as plasma jets, where the estimation of the plasma volume is more complex to be approximated. According to most of the existing literature, the power that is applied to the gas can predict the production of RONS. However, due to inconsistencies in reporting and the difficulties of measuring the RONS, this correlation could not be quantified in the current study. From our results, the dissipated power per plasma volume seems to have an important effect on the decontamination efficacy of NTP with the DBD setup.

The majority of studies in the literature report an increase in the decontamination efficacy of NTP through the increase in power density. However, there are a few studies that determine a decrease in decontamination efficacy with increasing power, through the decrease of ozone species, in favor of other species that are less effective (Bauer et al., 2017; Pavlovich et al., 2013). These studies suggest that there should be a threshold for maximum inactivation efficacy, however, this threshold is not consistent, so if it exists it should be system and ambient conditions specific. Also, according to Wan et al. (2021), the other ROS and RNS formed with higher voltage (and power) are more efficient than ozone and it could be that strong electric fields could also be influencing bacterial inactivation except for the RONS (Wan et al., 2021). Thus, the power density (dissipated power per plasma volume (W/cm^3)) has been proposed in the current study to be reported in the experiments related to NTP as a basis for comparison of decontamination efficacy results.

The modeling framework started from the simple approach of multiple linear regression and was compared to more complex approaches using machine learning. The final modeling strategies are rather complex for the number of observations that are available at the moment, but so are the parameters and the variability involved in NTP inactivation. The linear regression with or without regularization showed a poor fit which could be mainly attributed to the high variance of the dataset, a significant amount of it cannot be explained with a linear model, using the predetermined parameters. The elastic net regularization did not improve the obtained results, which could be due to the limited parameters selected that were already determined from the exploratory data analysis. XGBoost and random forests, followed by support vector machines showed higher R^2 values on the test dataset when compared to artificial neural networks. This aligns with existing literature which suggests that while deep learning has achieved remarkable success in

various fields as image, audio, and text processing, often underperforms on small, tabular datasets (Grinsztajn et al., 2022; Shwartz-Ziv & Armon, 2022).

Based on the exploratory data analysis, the frequency, the product temperature, the dominant working gas, the type of cells, and the selective recovery medium (yes, no) were excluded from the set of potential predictors, before the modeling steps. Our results showed that dissipated power per plasma volume and matrix category, followed by the microbial genus and the pH were the most important parameters affecting decontamination efficacy. Regarding the effect of pH, higher pH values seemed to increase the decontamination efficacy, which seemed contrary to what would be expected based on other technologies such as thermal treatment but given the mean pH value of 6.8 of our dataset (Supplementary Table 3), both higher and lower pH values would be expected to increase the decontamination efficacy. Also, the pH could partially mask the effect of other correlated parameters for which there were not enough data or variation to accurately separate them. For example, in one study included in the database, the NaCl concentration changed along with the pH, and this adaptation to osmotic stress and suboptimal pH before CAP treatment led to lower inactivation efficacy (Smet et al., 2019). XGBoost showed some differences in this order, but these four were still the most important parameters affecting decontamination efficacy, and with the same direction, together with the sample area. However, the effect of the sample area was condition-dependent according to XGBoost, and opposite than expected through multiple linear regression (i.e., higher sample area, higher decontamination efficacy), so it was not considered in the list of the most important parameters according to both models i.e., dissipated power per plasma volume and matrix category, pH and the microbial genus. The pH and the microbial genus are ranked lower than dissipated power per plasma volume and matrix category, because they were just significant in the multiple linear regression model. The effect of the upper electrode shape was not consistent for both models. The least correlated parameters according to both models were: peak-to-peak voltage, frequency, relative humidity, product temperature, dominant working gas, type of cells (vegetative, biofilm), and selective recovery medium (yes, no).

The unexplained variability of the quantitative models for DBD (Section 3) has to do with multiple reasons. Some of this part has to do with the experimental bias included in the original studies (Garre et al., 2023), and more importantly with unspecified practices of each research team and the specific goals of each study that are difficult to capture with meta-regression models. The specific goals that were not captured with the current study are the generation cycle of the biofilms before treatment (from 1st to 5th generation cycle), if the cells were grown before treatment in preculture, planktonic or surface mode, different proportions of working gases (even though the dominant gas was remaining the same) and the effect of dual-species presence in the matrix. Regarding the different salt concentrations that were used in some matrices, it should be noted that for these cases the authors listed also different pH levels for the corresponding cases i.e., pH 7.4 for 0% NaCl concentration, pH 6.5 for 2% NaCl concentration, and pH 5.5 for 6% NaCl concentration. All the aforementioned parameters are expected to be highly associated with the parameters that were already reported (microbial genus, strain, growth stage, type of cells, working gas, pH). Other parameters that are assumed to affect the decontamination efficacy i.e., flow rate, temperature, and water activity (Anuntagool et al., 2023), although reported in our structural database, there was not enough variation in our dataset to see their actual contribution. Useful parameters related to the solid surface properties (e.g., roughness, porosity) were not reported in any of the studies included in our database, while information regarding the protein and lipid profile and concentration was limited and difficult to compare consistently. Thus, we expect the establishment of guidelines regarding the crucial parameters that should be reported in NTP microbial inactivation studies such as the dissipated power per plasma volume, and other technical

characteristics of the setup used for the experiment as well as more detailed information about the product intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics would improve the research quality and would make comparisons more robust, while the implication of the produced results would make the technology more applicable.

5. Conclusion

This study used active learning, for the first time in the field of food microbiology for an efficient literature review and investigated the decontamination efficacy of NTP, qualitatively for various setups and quantitatively for DBD. It established the concept of dissipated power per plasma volume as a valuable metric of microbial inactivation. Using conventional and machine learning approaches, it was shown that dissipated power per plasma volume and matrix category, followed by the microbial genus and the pH affect significantly the decontamination efficacy and explain a significant amount of the variability. The machine learning framework that was established in this study could be a valuable tool for future research.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

George Pampoukis: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Marcel H. Zwietering:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Heidy M.W. den Besten:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2024.103773>.

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